

Ayurvedic management of *Vatarakta* with special reference to Gout: A Case Study

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Abstract

Vatarakta is a disease explained in Ayurveda involving *Vata Dosha* imbalance affecting *Rakta Dhatu*, where the *Vayu* gets aggravated due to long distance rides on animals like elephants, camels, horses, and on the other hand *Rakta* or blood gets vitiated by the consumption of *Lavana*, *Amla*, *Katu*, *Kshara* etc. The *Vata*, whose passages are blocked by *Rakta* further undergoes vitiation and further contaminates the *Rakta* or blood. The blood vitiated by *Vayu* later burns the whole blood in the body and later gravitates towards the foot. This vicious amalgamation of vitiated *Vata* and *Rakta* is called *Vatarakta*. *Vatarakta* can even be correlated to Gout on the basis of etiopathology.

A 45 years old female patient approached the OPD with the chief complaints of: Right great toe pain, swelling along with discoloration. Right ankle joint pain, swelling along with burning sensation of b/l sole. Right wrist joint pain along with difficulty in movements & Generalised weakness was also seen. All the above complains were since 4 months. The patient was given completely Ayurvedic medicines such as *Kaishor guggul*, *Amrutadi guggul*, *Sanshamani Vati*, *Guduchi kwath* for oral consumption & *Pinda Tail (Sukhoshna)* for local application & sarvanganadisweda with dashmool kwath for 2 months, follow up was taken on every week for 2 months. The results were remarkably seen. Hence this study was taken to prove that Ayurvedic management has remarkable results in *Vatarakta* (Gout).

Keywords: *Vatarakta*; Gout; *Vatadosha*; *Raktadhatu*; *lavana*; *Amla*; *Katu*; *Kshara*

1. Introduction

Vatarakta is a painful condition. The condition develops suddenly and reoccurs after treatment. When aggravated *Vata* is obstructed by aggravated *Rakta*, this obstructed *Vata* again vitiates the *Rakta*. This pathological state is known as *Vatashonitam* or *Vatarakta*.

Vatarakta is described in details in *Charak Samhita* and other *Samhita* also. In *Sushrut Samhita*, *Vatarakta* is described in *Vata Vyadhiadhyaya*. In *Vatarakta* mainly small joints of feet and hands are affected. On the basis of etiology and symptomatology Gout is similar to that of *Vatarakta*. Gout is also called metabolic arthritis. Gout is an abnormality of Uric acid metabolism that results in *hyperuricemia*, deposition of monosodium urate crystal in joints, soft tissue and renal tubules^[1].

1.1. Types of *Vatarakta*

1.1.1. *Vatapradhana Vatarakta*

When *Vata* is severely vitiated in *Vatarakta* symptoms like pain, twitching, pricking pain, swelling which is dry and black, stiffness of body parts, aversion or aggravation of symptoms by cold, numbness etc will dominate the picture.

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1.1.2. Raktapradhana Vatarakta

When Rakta is severely vitiated in Vatarakta, the symptoms like swelling, severe pain and pricking pain, copper colour of the skin, itching and moistness predominate.

1.1.3. Pitta pradhana Vatarakta

When Pitta is severely vitiated in Vatarakta, the symptoms like severe burning sensation, sweating, fainting, thirst, tenderness, pain, swelling and suppuration will be predominantly found.

1.1.4. Kaphapradhana Vatarakta

When Kapha is severely vitiated in Vatarakta, the symptoms like numbness, heaviness, moistness, unctuousness and coldness will prevail.

1.2. Vatarakta is also of 2 types based on its location

1.2.1. Uttana Vatarakta

The disease pathology afflicts the superficial tissues i.e. skin and muscles, the symptoms are also limited to the skin. In this type, the symptoms moreover look like a skin disease or Kushta with skin lesions and muscle pain.

1.2.2. Gambhira Vatarakta

The disease pathology involves blood and other deeper tissues like bone and joints and also the internal viscera. This is moreover a systemic illness and the symptoms are more complicated. This moreover looks like a joint pathology because the joint symptoms are more than the skin presentation.

2. Case Report

A 45 years old female patient approached the OPD with the chief complaints of Right great toe pain, swelling along with discoloration, Right ankle joint pain, swelling along with burning sensation of b/l sole, Right wrist joint pain along with difficulty in movements & Generalised weakness was also seen. All the above complains were since 4 months.

No H/o DM/HTN/Asthma.

2.1. History of Personal Illness

The patient was normal 4 months before. She developed swelling in right great toe along with discoloration and right feet swelling along with b/l sole burning sensation and lumbar pain. Patient was under multiple treatment one after the other.

After a lot of treatment the patient finally got admitted in SSAM, Hadapsar for Ayurvedic treatment.

2.2. Personal History

- Occupation- housewife
- Bad habits- nil
- Akrti- madhayam
- Bala- heen

2.3. On examination-

- BP- 130/80,
- P-86/min, SPO2- 98%,
- RS- B/l clear
- CVS- S1S2 normal
- P/A- soft & non tender
- Joint- swelling, redness & stiffness in right great toe, ankle & wrist joint

2.4. Investigations

- Hb- 10.4gm%
- ESR- 59mm/hr
- CRP- 41
- RA Factor- negative
- ASO Titer- negative
- Serum Uric Acid- 17
- CXR (PA)- Normal
- 2D echo cardiogram- Normal

Objective

To study the effect of Ayurvedic treatment in the management of Vatarakta.

3. Material and methods

3.1. Method

Centre of Study SSAM, Hadapsar, pune. Simple Random Single Case Study.

Treatment was given & patient was observed for the period of 2 months. Follow up was taken weekly i.e. after every 7 days.

3.2. Material

With daily Treatment and Prognosis Clinical examination of the patient revealed regression of symptoms due to our Ayurvedic Management.

Table 1 Gradation of symptoms according to WHO scoring pattern²

Symptoms	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4
Swelling	No swelling	Slightswelling	Moderateswelling	Severeswelling	
Discoloration	Normal coloration	Near to normal which looks like normal to distantobserver	Reddish coloration	Slight reddish black discoloration	Blackish discoloration
Burning Sensation	No burning	Mild burning	Moderateburning	Severeburning	
Pain	No pain	Mild pain	Moderate pain but no difficulty inmoving	Slightly difficulty in moving dueto pain	Much difficulty

3.3. Treatment

Table 2 Treatment given

Sr.No	Dravya	Dose	Duration	Anupana
1	<i>Kaishorguggul</i>	250 mg	TDS	Lukewarm water afterfood
2	<i>Amrutadiguggul</i>	250 mg	TDS	Lukewarm water afterfood
3	<i>SanshamaniVati</i>	250 mg	TDS	Lukewarm water afterfood
4	<i>Guduchikwath</i>	15 ml	BD	Lukewarm water afterfood
5	<i>PindaTail</i>	local application	BD	
6	<i>Dashmoolkwath</i>	Localapplication	OD	

Table 3 Observation

Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment
Rt. great toe pain	4	2
Rt. great toe swelling	3	1
Rt great toe redness	2	1
Rt ankle pain	4	2
Rt ankle swelling	3	1
Bilateral burning sensation of sole	2	0
Rt. wrist pain	3	1
Rt wrist movement difficulty	1	0
Generalised weakness	2	1

Table 4 Changes in Serum Uric acid levels

Before treatment	17
After treatment	10.3

4. Results

The patient had started improving after 8th day there was overall recovery as case had reached at *Upadrava*, so it needs time to cure but with Ayurvedic treatment it has relief in all the subjective and objective parameters.

5. Discussion

Table 5 Action of Drugs in the Management of Vatarakta

Sr no.	Drug	Action
1	Kaishor Guggul	<i>Tridoshaghna Rasayana Vatrakta adhikar Sharangdhar Samhita madhyam khanda 7/70-81</i>
2	Amrutadi Guggul	<i>Tridoshaghna Shula nashak Vatrakta adhikar Sharangdhar Samhita madhyam khanda 7/70-81</i>
3	Sanshamani Vati	<i>Shula nashak Amapachan Sidharog sanghrah, Jwaraadhikara AFI Vol.II</i>
4	Guduchi Kwath	<i>Tridoshaghna Vatraktanashak</i>
5	Pinda tail snehan	<i>Vedanahara Vataraktanasahak Charak vatarakta chikitsa</i>
6	Dashamool Kwathswed	<i>Tridoshaghna Vatanashak</i>

5.1. Mode of action of Snehana³

Snehana helps in the proper Gati of Vata, brings Gaatra Mardavata and removes the Srothorodha. Sneha overcomes Rukshatha by its Snigdha property and the Sanga is corrected.

Mode of action of Swedana⁴: Ushnaguna of Swedana does Srothoshuddi and Amapachana, so it relieves stiffness. Due to elimination of Keldra, lightness is achieved. Stamba, Gaurav, Swayathu are the symptoms of Vatarakta. To relieve these symptoms Swedana is helpful.

6. Conclusion

Since therapy for *Vatarakta* and its complications has limitations in other patients, Ayurvedic management of chronic *Vatarakta* can be effective therapy. On understanding proper *Nidan*, *Lakshana* and *Samprapti* of *Vatarakta* one can very well keep it under the heading of *Vata Vyadhi* and treat it successfully with *Ayurvedic* treatment. With proper understanding of *Dosha*, *Dushya* and *Vyadhi Awastha* we can manage *Vatarakta*. The medicines given to the patient mainly fall under the categories of *Tiktakashay rasa*, *Laghu*, *rooksha guna*, *Ushna*, *veerya* and either *Kapha vatahara* or *Pitta vatahara* mainly used for *Deepan paachan* and *Raktaprasadana* with *Shoola and Shothagna karma*. The patient had 80% relief and the laboratory findings of Serum Uric acid had lowered significantly. Therefore the given Ayurvedic treatment was successfully in curing the disease without landing into further complications.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was taken from the patient.

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